

Low Speed Course-Keeping and Zigzag Manoeuvres of the KSUPRAMAX Bulk Carrier in Waves

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Abstract. Manoeuvring performances of ships in waves are significantly different from those in calm water. Reliable prediction techniques on the ship's manoeuvrabilities in waves are required at the early design stage for its safe operations in actual seas. In particular, attentions should be paid to the ship's course-keeping and changing abilities which become more important in rough waves. In this study, course-keeping and zigzag manoeuvres of a 'KSUPRAMAX' model ship which has a supramax class bulk carrier hull form are experimentally investigated. The full-scale ship length is 192 m, a 1/64-scaled model ship is constructed for free-running model tests in Ocean Engineering Basin of Korea Research Institute of Ships and Ocean Engineering (KRISO). At first, turning circle tests are repeatedly conducted in long-crested irregular waves with the model propulsion point corresponded to the full-scale design speed of 14.5 knots. Equivalent regular waves that show similar turning circle trajectories and approach speeds compared to irregular waves are searched. Next, course-keeping tests are performed in irregular and equivalent regular waves with wave incident angles of 0 to 180 degrees at speeds lower than 5 knots. Low speed course-keeping paths, check helms, and drift angles in equivalent regular waves are close to those in irregular waves. 3-DoF manoeuvring simulation models are constructed based on captive model tests and empirical methods. Since the wave drift forces are equal to sums of hydrodynamic forces acting on the hull, the propeller, and the rudder during course-keeping manoeuvres, wave drift forces are identified from course-keeping simulations. Zigzag tests are also conducted in equivalent regular waves with approaching conditions which are the same as those in course-keeping tests, zigzag behaviors are simulated by the present models including wave drift forces identified. Course-keeping and changing abilities are discussed with considerations of wave drift forces which are varied with wave incident angles.

Keywords: *KSPURAMAX bulk carrier, Free-running model test, Course-keeping ability, Zigzag manoeuvre, Wave drift force*

1 Introduction

Ship's manoeuvrabilities are conventionally evaluated in calm water, which are different from those in a seaway due to environmental loads. At an early design stage, it is necessary to predict manoeuvring performance of a ship in waves as well as in calm water for its safe operations in seas. Moreover, installed engine powers of new-built ships are recently decreased to meet EEDI requirements which aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Attentions should be paid to check whether ships have sufficient manoeuvrabilities for operating in adverse weather conditions.

In adverse conditions, ship advance speeds are decreased, manoeuvrabilities of ships are remarkably different from those in calm water. Since ships should overcome violent environmental loads and keep or change their courses by their own steering systems, course-keeping and changing abilities of ships are of particular importance in such situations. As in conventional IMO standard manoeuvring tests, course-keeping and changing abilities of ships can be evaluated through zigzag manoeuvring performances. In addition, in adverse weather condition under strong environmental loads, asymmetric behaviors of ships such as hull drifts and check helms for keeping straight courses need to be investigated in detail.

There are some previous studies on course-keeping or zigzag abilities of ships in waves through experimental or numerical techniques. Hirayama and Kim (1994) performed zigzag model tests of a tanker in long and short crest irregular waves generated in a towing tank, simulations by manoeuvring models including wave drift forces are compared with model test results [1]. Yasukawa and Adnan (2006) experimentally investigated motions and wave drift forces of a container model in regular head and beam waves, effects of drift angles on wave drift forces

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were discussed, Yasukawa (2008) validated zigzag and stopping manoeuvring simulations through comparison with free-running model tests [2][3]. In a research by Sprenger et al. (2017), free-running turn and zigzag model tests of a KVLCC2 tanker and a DTC container were performed in four European institutes and were analyzed within the framework of SHOPERA project [4]. Zhang et al. (2017) carried out two-time scale simulations on turn and zigzag manoeuvres of a S175 container in regular waves and compared them with model test results [5]. Wang et al. (2018) investigated standard zigzag manoeuvring characteristics of an ONRT model in regular waves by using CFD solver [6]. Sanada et al. (2018) carried out course-keeping and manoeuvring model tests of an ONRT in various regular waves, in particular, time-averaged and harmonic amplitudes of ship motions and rudder angles during course-keeping tests are analyzed in various wave incident angles [7]. Kim et al. (2022) performed free-running CFD calculations of a KCS model and analyzed low-speed course-keeping and turning abilities of the model in different wave incident angles [8]. Suzuki et al. (2023, 2024) carried out free-running course-keeping model tests of a KVLCC1 tanker in regular short waves and compared them with numerical simulations considering steady wave drift forces and moments obtained by captive model tests and CFD [9][10].

In this study, course-keeping and zigzag abilities of a ‘KSUPRAMAX’ bulk carrier in waves are investigated by free-running model tests. At first, 35° turning circle tests are carried out in long-crested irregular and various regular waves. The significant height and the peak period of long-crested irregular waves are selected with consideration of adverse weather conditions defined in an IMO minimum propulsion power guideline [11]. Equivalent regular waves are determined so that model ship approach speeds and trajectories in irregular waves are similar to those in regular waves. It is also confirmed that low speed course-keeping abilities depending on wave incident angles in irregular waves are similar to those in equivalent regular waves. By using steady state variables of the hull, the propeller, and the rudder in course-keeping tests, wave drift forces and moments depending on incident angles are identified through modular type manoeuvring models. Low speed 10°/10° starboard and port zigzag tests are conducted in equivalent regular waves with various incident angles. Zigzag abilities in waves are significantly different from those in calm water, and are varied depending on wave incident angles, i.e. wave drift forces and moments. Zigzag behaviors depending on wave incident angles are analyzed with considerations of wave drift forces identified.

2 Free-running model test

2.1 Model ship and test basin

Free-running model tests are carried out with a 1/64-scaled modelship of ‘KSUPRAMAX’ in this study. The full-scale ship is a 66,000 DWT supramax bulk carrier, which were used in recent CFD or model test studies on mainly its added resistances in waves [12][13][14]. Main particulars of full-scale and modelships are summarized in Table 1. Figure 1 shows the body plan and the scaled model ship constructed. The ship geometry and test data can be downloaded from KRISO website [15], otherwise, can be provided via the corresponding author’s email.

Table 1. Main particulars of full-scale and model ships (design draft)

Particular	Full-scale	Model
Scale ratio (λ)	1	64
Length between perpendiculars (L) [m]	192.0	3.000
Breadth (B) [m]	36.0	0.563
Fore / aft draft (T_F / T_A) [m]	11.2 / 11.2	0.175 / 0.175
Displacement (∇) [m ³]	65028.2	0.248
LCB (fwd, +) [m]	5.773	0.090
Yaw radius of gyration (k_{zz}) [L]	0.250	0.238
Metacentric height (GM) [m]	-	0.080
Propeller diameter (D_P) [m]	6.0	0.094
Rudder lateral area (A_R) [m ²]	45.91	0.0112

Figure 1. Body plan (left) and 1/64-scaled model ship (right) of KSUPRAMAX bulk carrier

Free-running model tests are conducted in Ocean Engineering Basin of Korea Research Institute of Ships and Ocean Engineering (KRISO) as described in Figure 2. The basin is 56 m in length, 30 m in beam, and 4.5 m in depth. Wave makers are installed along short and long ends of the basin. For present model tests, regular and long-crested irregular waves are generated by short end wave makers. Ship motions, propulsion and steering signals are measured by onboard PC mounted on the model, and all synchronized signals are sent to the ground control PC wirelessly. Three prisms are fixed on the model deck. They are traced by three total station devices on the ground so that the 3-dimensional ship positions can be measured automatically, which have been updated compared to the previous 2-dimensional measurement system [16][17]. Figure 3 shows the coordinate system used in the present study. O-XY is a space-fixed coordinate, X-coordinate is set toward the model ship heading when each test starts. o-xy is a body-fixed coordinate, whose origin is located on the midship of the ship.

Figure 2. Free-running model test in KRISO Ocean Engineering Basin

Figure 3. Coordinate system

2.2 Test program

Free-running turning circle and zigzag tests are carried out in calm water at the model propulsion points of 19.0 and 8.0 RPS which correspond to the full-scale speeds of 14.5 (design speed) and 5.0 knots, respectively. 35° portside turning circle tests are conducted in long-crested irregular waves and several kinds of regular waves at 19.0 RPS. Based on above turning circle test results, one specific regular wave condition is selected. At the propulsion point of 8.0 RPS, course-keeping and 10/10 zigzag tests are performed in irregular and selected regular waves with varying wave incident angles. Total program is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Free-running model test program (SB: starboard, PS: port side)

Test	Wave	RPS [/s]	Wave incident angle [°] (e.g. 180°: head wave)
35° SB, PS Turn	Calm water	19.0 (corr. 14.5 knots)	-
35° SB, PS Turn 10°/10° SB, PS Zigzag		8.0 (corr. 5.0 knots)	
35° PS Turn	Irregular (Hs= 4.5m, Tp=12.0s)	19.0	180
	Regular (H= 2.589~4.500 m, T= 8.520~12.000 s)		
Course-keeping	Irregular (Hs= 4.5m, Tp=12.0s)	8.0	180, 150, 120, 90, 60, 30, 0
	Regular (H= 2.878 m, T= 9.780 s)		
10°/10° SB, PS Zigzag	Irregular (Hs= 4.5m, Tp=12.0s)	8.0	180, 150, 90, 30, 0
	Regular (H= 2.878 m, T= 9.780 s)		

3 Search of ‘equivalent regular waves’ corresponding to the adverse condition

3.1 Turning circle tests at 19.0 RPS (corr. full-scale 14.5 knots in calm water)

To maintain the manoeuvrability of ships in adverse weather conditions, IMO interim guideline for determining minimum propulsion power of ships was proposed [11]. In the guideline, adverse weather condition is defined as Table 3. For the present full-scale KSUPRAMAX bulk carrier, the significant wave height and peak period can be determined as Table 4. Wind loads are not considered in this study.

Table 3. Adverse weather condition (IMO, 2021)

Ship length [m]	Significant wave height [m]	Peak wave period [s]	Mean wind speed [m/s]
L > 250	6.0	7.0 ~ 15.0	22.6
200 ≤ L ≤ 250	Linearly interpolated depending on ship length		
L < 200	4.5	7.0 ~ 15.0	19.0

Table 4. Long-crested irregular wave condition in the present study

Significant wave height [m]	Peak wave period [s]
4.5	12.0

Figure 4. 35° PS turns in irregular waves (left) and definition of drifting distance and angle (SIMMAN,2023) (right)

At first, the model propulsion point is fixed to 19.0 RPS which corresponds to the full-scale 14.5 knots in calm water, 35° portside turning circle tests are carried out in long-crested irregular waves determined in Table 4. Five repetition test results are analyzed in Figure 4. Due to the wave drift forces and moments, turning circle trajectories are drifted in waves. Definition of trajectory drifting distance and angle are described on the right of Figure 4 [18]. Statistically, the present model ship is drifted approximately two times ship length during a 360° turn in irregular waves. The approach speed is 14.5 knots in calm water, whereas the mean value of approach speeds is reduced by 11.3 knots in irregular waves.

Wave energy flux per unit crest length (P_W [W/m]) are theoretically formulated in both regular and long-crested irregular waves, respectively, which are shown in Eqs. (1) and (2) [19]. ρ is the density of water, g is the gravitational acceleration, ζ_a is the amplitude of the incident wave, c_G is the group velocity. f is the wave frequency, $S(f)$ is the spectral density function of incident irregular waves. H_S and T_E are the significant wave height and the energy period, respectively. T_E is defined as Eq. (3) [20].

$$P_{W(regular)} = \frac{1}{2} \rho g \zeta_a^2 c_G = \frac{1}{32\pi} \rho g^2 H^2 T \quad (1)$$

$$P_{W(irregular)} = \rho g \int_0^\infty c_G(f) S_i(f) df = \frac{1}{64} \rho g^2 H_S^2 T_E \quad (2)$$

$$T_E = m_{-1}/m_0, \quad m_n = \int_0^\infty f^n S_i(f) df \quad (3)$$

When Eq. (1) equals to Eq. (2), ‘equivalent regular waves’ whose energy flux is identical to that of long-crested irregular waves are estimated as Table 5.

Table 5. Equivalent regular wave condition

Regular wave height, H	Regular wave period, T
$H = H_S/\sqrt{2}$	$T = T_E$

In order to investigate the model ship operated in the equivalent regular waves in Table 5 shows manoeuvring performances which are similar to those in long-crested irregular waves, 35° turning circle tests are carried out in various regular waves as described in Table 6. ‘REG03’ is the estimated condition in Table 5. Regular wave heights are varied from $H_S/2$ to H_S , periods are changed to T_Z , T_M , and T_P , respectively. T_Z , T_M , and T_P are zero-crossing, mean, and peak periods on irregular waves energy spectrum.

Results of 35° turning circle tests at 19.0 RPS in regular waves are analyzed in Figure 5. In the viewpoint of wave energy, ship approach speeds and trajectory drifting distances are focused on. Both are deeply related to wave drift forces and moments in longitudinal and lateral directions. REG03 shows turn trajectory drifting distance which is similar to that in irregular waves as anticipated, but the ship approach speed in REG03 is lower than that in irregular waves. The added resistance in REG03 is expected to be larger than that in irregular waves due to larger relative ship motions, although wave energies in both waves are theoretically identical to each other.

Table 6. Regular wave conditions (REG01 to REG06)

Height \ Period	Period	T_Z (8.520s)	T_M (9.276s)	T_E (10.284s)	T_P (12.000s)
	Height				
$H_S/2$ (2.250m)	(2.250m)	-	-	REG05	-
$H_S/\sqrt{2}$ (3.182m)	(3.182m)	REG01	REG02	REG03	REG04
H_S (4.500m)	(4.500m)	-	-	REG06	-

Figure 5. Approach speeds (left) and trajectory drifting distances (right) in REG01 to REG06

Interestingly, trajectory drifting distances in regular waves are proportional to wave slopes. To maintain the trajectory drifting distance, and to increase the ship approach speed, REG07 and REG08 are additionally generated as shown in Table 7. Wave slopes of REG07 and REG08 are the same as that of REG03.

Table 7. Additional regular wave conditions (REG07 and REG08)

Height	Period	T_M (9.276s)	$(T_E + T_M)/2$ (9.780s)	T_E (10.284s)
(2.589m)		REG08	-	-
(2.878m)		-	REG07	-
$H_S / \sqrt{2}$	(3.182m)	-	-	REG03

Figure 6. Approach speeds (left) and trajectory drifting distances (right) in REG07 and REG08 as well as REG03

Results of approach speeds and trajectory drifting distances are described in Figure 6. Both the approach speed and the trajectory drifting distance in ‘REG07’ are similar to those in irregular waves. Therefore, ‘REG07’ is determined as the equivalent regular waves. Turning trajectories in irregular and regular (REG07) waves are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. 35° PS turns in irregular waves (left) and in regular waves REG07 (right)

3.2 Course-keeping manoeuvres at 8.0 RPS in REG07 (corr. full-scale 5.0 knots in calm water)

Figure 8. Trajectories, check helms, drift angles, and ship speeds of course-keeping tests in irregular waves (left) and in regular waves REG07 (right)

In irregular waves and equivalent regular waves previously determined, low speed course-keeping tests are conducted with varying wave incident angles. Model propeller rotation rate is fixed to 8.0 RPS, which corresponds to the full-scale 5.0 knots in calm water. Wave incident angles are varied from 180° to 0° with the interval of 30°. Figure 8 shows course-keeping trajectories, time averaged check helms, drift angles, and ship speeds, which are also introduced in the previous study by Kim et al. (2024) [21]. Low speed course-keeping manoeuvres in equivalent regular waves are considerably similar to those in irregular waves, although time averaged values in irregular waves are quite varied depending on the encountered wave elevations.

4 Identification of wave drift forces and moments

4.1 3-DoF manoeuvring simulation model

To identify wave drift lateral forces and moments depending on wave incident angles, 3-DoF modular type manoeuvring models are used. Horizontal plane manoeuvres of the ship are represented by Eq. (1). Subscript H, P, and R denote force and moment components acting on the hull, the propeller, and the rudder.

$$\begin{aligned} m(\dot{u} - vr - x_G r^2) &= X_H + X_P + X_R \\ m(\dot{v} + ur + x_G \dot{r}) &= Y_H + Y_R \\ I_{zz} \dot{r} + m x_G (\dot{v} + ur) &= N_H + N_R \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Hull, propeller, and rudder forces and moments can be formulated as Eqs. (2) to (4).

$$\begin{aligned} X_H &= X_{\dot{u}} \dot{u} + X_{uu} u^2 + X_{vv} v^2 + X_{vr} vr + X_{rr} r^2 + X_{vvvv} v^4 \\ Y_H &= Y_{\dot{v}} \dot{v} + Y_{\dot{r}} \dot{r} + Y_v v + Y_r r + Y_{vvv} v^3 + Y_{rrr} r^3 + Y_{vvr} v^2 r + Y_{vrr} vr^2 \\ N_H &= N_{\dot{v}} \dot{v} + N_{\dot{r}} \dot{r} + N_v v + N_r r + N_{vvv} v^3 + N_{rrr} r^3 + N_{vvr} v^2 r + N_{vrr} vr^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$X_P = (1 - t) \rho n^2 D_P^4 \cdot K_T \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} X_R &= -(1 - t_R) F_N \sin \delta \\ Y_R &= -(1 + a_H) F_N \cos \delta \\ N_R &= -(x_R + a_H x_H) F_N \cos \delta \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In Eqs. (3) and (4), detailed characteristics of the propeller and the rudder are obtained by Eqs. (5) and (6).

$$\begin{aligned} K_T &= f(J) \\ J &= \frac{u_P}{n D_P} \\ u_P &= (1 - w_P) u, \quad w_P = w \cdot \exp(-C_P \beta_P^2), \quad \beta_P = \beta - x_P' r' \\ &\quad (C_P = C_P^+ \text{ when } \beta_P > 0, \quad C_P = C_P^- \text{ when } \beta_P < 0) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_N &= \frac{1}{2} \rho A_R U_R f_\alpha \sin \alpha_R \\ U_R &= \sqrt{u_R^2 + v_R^2}, \quad \alpha_R = \delta - \tan^{-1}(v_R/u_R) \\ u_R &= \epsilon u_P \sqrt{\eta \left[1 + \kappa \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{8K_T}{\pi J^2}} - 1 \right) \right]^2 + (1 - \eta)} \\ v_R &= \gamma_R (v + l_R r), \quad \beta_R = \beta - l_R' r' \\ &\quad (\gamma_R = \gamma_R^+ \text{ when } \beta_R > 0, \quad \gamma_R = \gamma_R^- \text{ when } \beta_R < 0) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Hydrodynamic coefficients in Eqs. (2) to (7) are obtained based on 1/26.087-scaled static HPMM tests [22] and empirical formulas. Present simulation models can predict calm water turn and zigzag behaviors of the model ship with high accuracy as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Comparison between simulations (red solid lines) and free-running model tests (blue dotted lines) in calm water

4.2 Wave drift forces and moments depending on wave incident angles

Figure 10. Equilibriums of surge, sway forces and yaw moments during a course-keeping manoeuvre (e.g. $\chi = 150^\circ$)

Hull, propeller, rudder, and wave drift forces are in equilibrium during a course-keeping test at the constant speed. Figure 10 describes an example of a course-keeping test with a wave incident angle of 150° . Since the propeller rotation rate is fixed to 8.0 RPS, and hull, rudder, and propeller state variables such as ship speeds, drift angles, check helms are given as Figure 8, hull, rudder, and propeller force and moment components are obtained through present manoeuvring models. Based on force and moment equilibriums, wave drift forces and moments can be estimated. Table 8 shows all force and moment components with wave incident angles during course-keeping manoeuvres.

Table 8. Estimation of wave drift forces and moments during course-keeping manoeuvres

Wave incident angle, χ	X_H	X_P	X_R	X_{WD} $= -X_H - X_P - X_R$	Y_H	Y_R	Y_{WD} $= -Y_H - Y_R$	N_H	N_R	N_{WD} $= -N_H - N_R$
[$^\circ$]	[N]	[N]	[N]	[N]	[N]	[N]	[N]	[Nm]	[Nm]	[Nm]
0	-0.634	0.451	-0.001	0.183	0.145	0.082	-0.227	0.242	-0.101	-0.141
30	-0.530	0.467	-0.004	0.067	0.114	0.143	-0.256	0.190	-0.177	-0.013
60	-0.449	0.468	-0.011	-0.008	0.493	0.266	-0.759	0.726	-0.330	-0.396
90	-0.509	0.427	-0.034	0.116	1.235	0.507	-1.742	1.453	-0.629	-0.824
120	-0.313	0.487	-0.010	-0.165	0.487	-0.147	-0.340	0.660	0.182	-0.842
150	-0.216	0.499	-0.005	-0.277	0.538	-0.093	-0.445	0.627	0.115	-0.742
180 (head)	-0.158	0.541	-0.001	-0.382	0.011	0.045	-0.056	0.018	-0.056	0.038

Figure 11. Non-dimensionalized surge, sway wave drift forces (top), and yaw wave drift moments (bottom) with wave incident angles

Wave drift forces and moments that vary with wave incident angles are key variables on determining course-keeping and changing abilities of the model ship in waves. Non-dimensionalized surge, sway wave drift forces and yaw wave drift moments are described in Figure 11.

Surge wave drift forces are negative (i.e. resistance increase) in head and bow waves, and are positive in quartering and following waves. Sway wave drift forces, of course, are large negative values in starboard beam waves compared to other wave incident angles. Yaw wave drift moments are particularly larger in bow waves than other wave incident angles, which means that it is hard to overcome wave drift moments by using rudder steering moments in bow waves.

It should be noted that effects of hull drift angles are considered on the present wave drift forces and moments estimation. In some previous researches, it was confirmed that wave drift forces and moments are significantly changed with hull drift angles [6][7]. Therefore, attentions should be paid to drift angles if readers compare the present estimated wave drift forces and moments with other numerical results.

5 Zigzag manoeuvres at 8.0 RPS in REG07

At the model propeller rotation rate of 8.0 RPS, $10^\circ/10^\circ$ zigzag tests are carried out with wave incident angles of 180° (head), 150° (bow), 90° (beam), 30° (quartering), and 0° (following waves). Steady approach states such as ship speeds, drift angles, and check helms are the same as those in previous course-keeping tests shown in Figure 8. Since check helms, i.e. initial rudder angles, are non-zero values, rudder commands are given as relative $+10^\circ$ or -10° from the check helm. For example, the check helm is -9.8° in beam waves. In such case, actual rudder commands in starboard and port directions are $+0.2^\circ$ and -19.8° , respectively. Zigzag trajectories, rudder and yaw angles are described in Figure 12. Rudder and yaw angles in calm water zigzags are also plotted in gray lines.

Figure 12. Free-running 10°/10° SB (left) and PS (right) zigzag tests at 8.0 RPS depending on wave incident angles

In Figure 12, 1st overshoot angles are especially increased in head waves. Since the approach speed in head waves is lowest due to the large added resistance, the rudder steering moment is insufficient. When the ship heading is changed to 10° or more, the ship encounters large wave drift moments in bow waves (see Figure 11), and cannot return to its initial course.

On the other hand, in beam waves, although the drift angle the check helm for keeping the ship heading are large (see Figure 8), 1st overshoot angles and elapsed times in zigzags are small compared to those in other incident angles. The course-changing ability of the ship is superior in beam waves, in spite of laterally biased wave drift forces and moments.

Figure 13. Comparisons of free-runs and simulations of 10°/10° SB zigzags at 8.0 RPS

$$\begin{aligned}
m(\dot{u} - vr - x_G r^2) &= X_H + X_P + X_R + X_{WD} \\
m(\dot{v} + ur + x_G \dot{r}) &= Y_H + Y_R + Y_{WD} \\
I_{zz} \dot{r} + m x_G (\dot{v} + ur) &= N_H + N_R + N_{WD}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

By substituting estimated wave drift forces and moments (see Figure 11) into right hand sides of Eq. (1), zigzag manoeuvres can be simulated by Eq. (8). During simulations wave drift forces and moments in Figure 11 are linearly interpolated for instantaneous wave incident angles. Figure 13 shows comparisons of 10°/10° SB zigzag histories from model tests and simulations in various wave incident angles. 1st overshoot angles in all 10°/10° zigzag model tests and simulations are compared in Figure 14. Zigzag simulations including wave drift forces and moments which are obtained from course-keeping model tests totally show good agreements with zigzag model tests. Therefore, the system identification of free-running course-keeping tests is the recommended procedure to estimate reliable wave drift forces and moments acting on the ship in waves. In particular, wave drift forces and moments are useful information to predict course-keeping and changing abilities of the ship.

Figure 14. 1st overshoot angles in 10°/10° SB (left) and PS (right) zigzags of free-runs and simulations

6 Conclusions

In this study, low speed course-keeping and zigzag manoeuvring characteristics of a KSUPRAMAX model ship are investigated through free-running model tests in waves. And manoeuvring simulations are utilized to derive wave drift forces and moments and to predict zigzag behaviors of the ship. Main conclusions are as follows.

- ◆ Long-crested irregular wave conditions are determined with consideration of the IMO minimum propulsion power guideline.
- ◆ 35° turning circle tests are conducted in long-crested irregular and various regular waves. ‘Equivalent regular waves’ which reproduce similar approach speeds and trajectory drifting distances compared to those in irregular waves are searched in the viewpoint of wave energies.
- ◆ Low speed course-keeping tests are performed in long-crested irregular and equivalent regular waves with varying wave incident angles. Course-keeping trajectories, check helms, drift angles, and speeds in equivalent regular waves are totally similar to those in long-crested irregular waves.
- ◆ Wave drift forces and moments depending on incident angles are identified by using manoeuvring simulation models.
- ◆ Low speed 10°/10° zigzag tests are carried out in regular waves with varying incident angles. In head waves the modelship cannot return to its initial course due to largely increased wave drift forces and moments, whereas the course-changing ability of the ship is not degraded in beam waves. Careful attention should be paid on course-changing manoeuvres during a ship’s operation in head or bow waves.

- ◆ Substituting identified wave drift forces and moments into manoeuvring models, zigzag manoeuvres are simulated in different wave incident angles. Zigzag simulations are in good agreements with free-running model tests.

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